

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Juned, Mansur, and Salam, Syahrul (2018), Maneuver of Digital Economy in Global Era: Indonesia's Economic Synergy and Compensation Political Strategy Encounter Indian Digital Expansion. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.1, No.3, 363-369.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.01.03.25

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

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Maneuver of Digital Economy in Global Era: Indonesia's Economic Synergy and Compensation Political Strategy Encounter Indian Digital Expansion

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Abstract

India has claimed itself as a country being able to adapt fast against digital technological development and moreover, it is able to create or innovate in the development of digital industry in the world. Tight competition among big countries with tremendous capital urges India to do the maneuver of business cooperation in the more sophisticated and modern sector, but it makes many parties enjoyable. As the region with a big population, ASEAN becomes the target of India, particularly Indonesia with adequate capital and direction of the government's policy towards the development of digital technology makes India as the focus of establishing digital cooperation. However, for Indonesia itself, it is not able to balance the human resources capacity. Therefore, this research tries to explain Indonesia's maneuver in digital business in ASEAN and Indonesia's anticipative measures against the maneuver.

Keywords: India, Digital Business, ASEAN, Compensation, Indonesia

1. Introduction

1.1 Globalization and Compensation Politics

Globalization is an effort to reach profit objectives from all sectors and it results from any cooperation and freedom of goods trade and service flows from all over the world without any state border lines. It is believed that it is able to bring welfare for all parties involved in the process. The belief is not without any basis because the globalization is considered to give opportunities for anyone to enjoy liberalization and capitalism. Day by day the globalization is able to facilitate inter-country and inter-region trade. However, trade liberalization causes income retribution and absolute loss for some societies. Therefore, a trade agreement can only increase the welfare of a nation if people who get advantages from the globalization can give compensation to those who are disadvantaged.

In Europe, the disadvantaged nations from the globalization are usually those that tremendously apply active social programs and intervention in manpower market. The United States is the biggest country involved in the

globalization. Despite supporting the free market, the social protection remains to prevail despite under the leadership of Democratic Party. Under the Republican Party, it tries to reduce the social protection in the United States. Trump government indirectly indicates that current globalization tends to support the groups who have skills and assets. Compensation politics is frequently used to justify the advantaged trade policy despite the promising compensation is frequently not implemented. The bad impact of the globalization results in some deteriorating for different parts of society, but with some compensation, they can be helped. Despite it can support them for a while; Dani Rodrik thinks that it will be useless if we do not think alternatives to change the existing globalization regulations (Rodrik 2017).

The condition finally pushes each country to be involved in the globalization. Of course, the countries consisting different entities are directly involved in the globalization itself, i.e., society. Appropriate to the initial objective, the globalization is to provide profit for society in any country. However, the current economic condition of developing countries until right now cannot be separated basically from the implication of conditionality's implementation on the basis of neoliberalism.

Dani Rodrik has stated about anticipative measures when he sees the facts that the developed countries have worries on the negative impact of the globalization. It should be paid more attention carefully. The relationship between free trade and public welfare does not go on automatically like the assumption of neoliberal thinkers. The implementation of free trade in the world trade condition is unequal. There remains manipulation and monopoly as well as unperfect competition plus no institution or policy so that the globalization cannot guarantee equal distribution. On the other hand, it will direct to the growth of poverty rate and economic difficulties for many parties.

Finally, it has been clearly seen that global economic management all this time is not built on the basis of a vision reflecting the joint interests of all states. It is based on the neoliberalism principles, the vision reflecting the interests of some developed countries. It is proved that the world economic development does not run equally. The biggest profit for the world economic activities remains under the domination of the developed countries. Meanwhile, liberalism-neoliberalism principles are successfully planted in the economic policies of many states throughout the world, these results in the shackle of possibility to reach the ideals of the world's poverty reduction that mostly occurs in the developing countries or some parts of society in the developed countries (Rodrik 2017).

In general, it can be concluded that the implementation of liberalism/neoliberalism in various schemes results in the vulnerability of state economic fundamentals against crisis and poverty particularly for groups of society who do not have any access and capacity to enter into the market. Moreover, the economic gap in various schemes undergoes the growth as the impact of liberalism/neoliberalism hegemony in the global economic management all this time (Chomsky 2011).

The United States' economic policy is truly the mix of protectionism, interventionism, free market, and liberalism. All policies are particularly directed to the demand of groups that implement the social policies; they are mostly rich people and those in power. For example, the United States always has active industrial policies like other industrial countries. It can be understood that private company system can only exist if there is any extensive intervention from the government. It is carried out to regulate the market and protect private capital.

The writer sees that there are two important consequences of the globalization. Firstly, the globalization expands the implementation of the third world's capital to industrial countries. In the Third World, there are two strata of society: a rich group of people who gets privileges and those who are in misery. Secondly, the structure of governance frequently relates to various business interests, and finally, it makes difficult to choose between giving priority to capture capital sources or people welfare. Therefore, political compensation is not the final solution to the existing problems for the globalization. It is only temporary medicine. When a society is not involved in the globalization, they will be hindered to capital sources for the regulations and laws give advantages for some parties (the rulers and capitalists).

2. Research Methods

The type of research used here is a qualitative research method. With the type of qualitative research method, the writer tries to explore and understand the attitude of India and Indonesia in relation to digital business and economic relationship (Creswell 2014, 4-5). The collecting data method that the writer had done is through the study of literature. With the study of literature, the writer collects data by reading literature, such as books,

magazines, journals, articles, official websites, newspapers, and reports. These should be relevant to support the study and complete the data in relation to the discussed topic.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Economic Globalization and India's Digital Expansion to ASEAN

Economic globalization can be defined as a phenomenon that reduces the geographical gap in economic activities. It is divided into several points, i.e., the globalization in the sector of production, trade, finance and capital flows. There are three things that become factors of the economic globalization, i.e., firstly, innovation in the sector of information technology, communication, and transportation. The second factor relates to the building of international institutions that regulate and try to reduce excise tax blocks; and thirdly, it builds the similarity of values and perception on the globalization led by the leading countries in the world.

The globalization in the sector of production and trade has the following characteristics: it occurs fragmentation or specialization of the supply chain in some countries so that it increases inter-state production chain. Moreover, it occurs trade with comparative advantage principles to minimize opportunity costs. Finally, it builds a multilateral trade system. In finance and capital flows, the economic globalization makes people easier and more profitable in the transaction of currency, credit, and others. Many international financial services have reduced its transaction cost globally.

Despite in many things, it is profitable, in some cases in Asia the economic globalization results in significant vulnerability towards a potential crisis. Therefore, it requires effort, and it does not only relate to crisis management but also an effort to prevent the crisis. In Southeast Asia, it has been established ASEAN Surveillance Process (ASP) and Asian Monetary Fund (AMF) for wider coverage to maximize cooperation and prevent a potential systematic crisis (Rajan 2001).

In the sector of taxation, the economic globalization basically has speeded up the goods trade flows. In this matter, the state should get profit. It results in a state policy that reduces all kinds of progressive taxes. Despite it sometimes reduces state income, the policy finally makes businessmen and people in general in the country profitable. If the taxes are reduced, and these will influence and increase goods prices and trade flows. It is a condition when the private sector definitely supports the state economy. On the other hand, anti-globalization can prove that not all people can get profit from the economic globalization. For example, those who do not have access and capital are frequently people in "the loss position" and disadvantaged. Therefore, efforts give fair compensation to those who have been disadvantaged is a must so as to believe that the goodness of the globalization keeps staying. We believe that the synergy between the private sector and the government is a must in the national development.

For example, Vihaan Network Limited (VNL), the India-based telecommunication and equipment providers, will help the government in the broadband connectivity development program for 2,000 villages in 2018. Despite the cooperation is carried out with the Indonesian government through the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology (Kominfo), it is part of the Universal Service Obligation program (USO). In the program, VNL will provide BTS in the remote areas that are far from the connectivity coverage. VNL will not only build BTS but also it operates them. It means that digital development in Indonesia mostly only involves India because the company becomes the super-technology provider. The network to be constructed will depend on the government's request whether it is 4G or 3G. However, until 2018 VNL has a total target of 2,000 connectivities and it can be implemented in the East of Indonesia, such as Sulawesi, Kalimantan or Papua through the programs of Kominfo. VNL provides the base transceiver station (BTS) in the form of independent GSM network or GSM extension for the existing PBX network. The system will get support automatic solar panel, and the panel battery filler occurs daytime. It is appropriate for the remote or rural area in Indonesia for economic power. Moreover, it can be used via off grid or on the grid with PLN's electricity transmission channel. An operator company that has used VNL's services is PT XL Axiata Tbk. The company with the stock code of EXCL in Indonesia Stock Exchange has expanded its connectivity to the 33 remote villages through the BTS installation in Papua and West Sulawesi.

Moreover, for the first time, Indian-ASEAN Conference and Exhibition called ICT Expo 2017 is held in Jakarta. The objective is to strengthen the relationship and commitment between India and ASEAN countries. Acting as the event organizer dated December 6 and 7, 2017 at Hotel Shangri-La Jakarta is Telecom Equipment and Services Export Promotion Council (TEPCT), India's telecommunication export services and promotion board. India-ASEAN ICT Expo 2017 becomes the platform for the convergence of telecommunication and information technology and business exchange between two regions (Secretariat 2015).

Either ASEAN countries or India can share their experiences concerning how to embrace digital technology, digital competency, and digital literacy. It is intended to find the life and change in all aspects of human society in each country again. The conference discusses training, regulation in the sector of communication, information technology convergence and telecommunication, e-health, e-government, e-education, e-finance, infrastructure, new technology, standardization, the tender of spectrum and optimization, permit issues as well as services providers. India-ASEAN ICT Expo 2017 meets more than 100 companies from India and ASEAN countries, and it attracts more than 2,000 exhibition visitors. The event also presents stakeholders of information technology and Telecom from India to Network, Meet and Plan so as to meet the dream of the economic cooperation with the ICT ASEAN industries.

Capital Investment Coordinating Agency (BKPM) records that in the last four years the investment in the sector of e-commerce and digital business has reached US\$2-3 billion per year. However, in the past, the investment in the sector was almost nothing. For the phenomena, Head of Capital Investment Coordinating Agency (BKPM) Thomas TrikasihLembong states that digital business has become an investment helper since 2014. It is possible that it has reached 15-20% of total foreign direct investment (FDI) each year in the sector. To attract more digital investment, BKPM initiates the relaxing regulations and laws. Firstly, it urges the Regional Government of Greater Jakarta Province to relax the regulations and laws so that digital companies can register their co-working spaces address as their head offices. Moreover, co-working spaces become a trend (ASEAN n.d.).

Greater Jakarta Province receives 95% of total investment in the sector of digital business. In the period of 2010-2017, the realized foreign investment in Greater Jakarta Province reached US\$34 billion with a total number of 27,601 projects having been realized. Therefore, the capital province occupies the second row of the investment destination region with trade as an investment's favorite destination. The second support is the relaxation of foreign manpower inflow regulations and laws particularly in digital business because Indonesia is the lack of skilled and expert manpower in the sector. Moreover, after discussing with Indonesia's unicorn leaders, he gets input to bring mentors from India and Australi for the training of national manpower. Right now he claims that the attention of RI President JokoWidodo has changed from physical infrastructures such as roads, bridges, and others to vocation education or non-physical infrastructure. It has objectives that Indonesia does not have loss moment of fast digital business growth and its impact to the national economy.

Indonesian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (Kadin) sets up India Bilateral Committee in its new executive board of directors to stimulate the realized target of total trade and investment value of US\$50 billion in 2025. Chief of Indonesian Chamber of Commerce and Industry (Kadin) Rosan P Roeslani admits that right now there is much potential economic cooperation to be developed between the two countries. The establishment of India Bilateral Committee is considered to become an initial step to identify the potential. The committee is expected to identify potentials or obstacles because in the 2016 CEO Forum the two countries have agreed to reach the ambitious target of 50:50 with total trade and investment value of US\$50 billion in 2025 (Mudassir 2018).

Two official visits of RI President Jokowi Widodo to India are considered as the commitment of strengthening the bilateral economic relationship between the two countries. Indonesia and India are predicted to become the 6th and 3rd biggest economic power in 2030 consecutively. Therefore, the two countries have potentially great investment and trade cooperation. Vice Chief of Kadin for International Relationship Sector Shinta Widjaja Kamdani expects that the committee is able to become the catalyst to reach the trade and investment target for the two countries' businessmen particularly in the six sectors having been approved previously, i.e., mining, infrastructure, manufacturing, pharmacy, digital and service sectors. Indonesia itself is the biggest trade partners in ASAN. India is the biggest palm oil from Indonesia. The country is also one of main export destination for coal from Indonesia.

For investment, India recorded the significant growth rate in 2017. It is more than five times if compared to the growth rate in the previous year, i.e., from US\$R55 million to US\$286.6 million. Therefore, it is an important to step for Indonesia's businessmen to increase better economic relationships with India's businessmen. Based on the data of Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS), the trade balance between Indonesia and India in 2016 amounted to US\$12.9 billion with total export of US\$10.2 billion and import of US\$2.1 billion. In 2017, Indonesia-India's trade balance year on year rose to 28.7% with a total export value of US\$14.08 billion and import value of US\$4.05 billion. However, the trade of the two countries in the period of January-March reduced 3.06% from US\$4.46 billion in 2017 to US\$4.33 billion in 2018.

3.2 Capacity of India's Digital Industry

With the support of demography, reformation, and globalization, India has grown fast in the next decade. Right now the new report from Morgan Stanley Research, it is found that two main initiatives have digitalized the cash-based economy and reform the old tax system. It is the way of India's expansion, and it makes India one of the countries with the biggest economic growth in the world and the fast growth in the world in the next ten years. The country has been in the strong track, and the digitalization occupies the Nominal Gross Domestic Product Growth as the highest one.

Despite the country encounters short-term growth issues, investors can expect to see the shift, and it is seen in the economic growth since 2018. All states that India's economy is ready to leap from the recent seventh position to the third biggest economy in 2027 with total Gross Domestic Product of US\$6 trillion. Its equity market is recently in the tenth ranking in the world, and it can leap to the fifth position with the financial services and consumerism stocks that lead.

Moreover, companies in India are the most direct beneficial receivers of vast global implication. The e-commerce growth, consumption growth, financial product, and investment can make India as the significant market for companies all over the world. In its initial digital revolution, India launches the biometric identification programs in 2010 called Aadhaar. It gives each individual the 12-digit number, and it can be verified with fingerprint or sloce scan. The project is almost done with most of 1.3 billion citizens in Indonesia registered with the state digital database (PTI 2018).

Jan Dhan estimates that 35% of India's households do not have bank accounts. Morgan Stanley predicts that most of India's households have access to bank accounts while the leap of cellular telephone uses makes easier for Indians to manage their accounts and do the transaction without cash money by using their mobile phone. Recently India has 800 million mobile phone users, and 430 million people have Internet access - one-third of India's population. The Internet access will double in the next 10 years and our estimates that 915 million people of India will be on the Internet in 2026.

Head of India's Research Center, Ridham Desai states that the government has been pushing the country towards the non-cash payment by limiting cash transaction value and providing digital payment incentive; the target is to increase the six-time digital transaction in this year.

Migrating Indian people from the cash-based transaction to the digital one either through bank debit card, credit card or cellular wallet, is the main catalyst for economic growth. The cash transaction inhibits economic growth such as the ease of business to avoid taxes, the restriction of e-commerce and the possible inhibition of customers and small-scale business to build credit. Moreover, the migration to digital is the main catalyst for economic expansion, the direct benefit receivers to cover a new way of customer finance companies and services, such as UPI, Mobile Wallet and Rupay Cards - the gateway domestic card payment launched three years ago - quickly results in two third of digital payment market in 2027.

India also carries out serious steps to fight against low digital literacy rate. It established the National Literacy Mission (National Digital Literacy Center) in August 2014. India tries to make one person in each household who has met digital literacy in 2020. India also has the commitment to training 147 million people in rural areas with the skill required to take technological benefits. It is a positive measure in creating more digital literary by increasing consciousness on the importance of digital literacy for national development.

3.3 India's Digital Cooperation with Other Countries in ASEAN: Malaysia and Singapore

India and Malaysia have agreed to increase cooperation in the digital and e-commerce initiatives. In the joint statement on the commemoration of the 60th diplomatic relationship, Malaysian Prime Minister Datuk Seri Najib Razak and his partner from India, Narendra Modi state that two countries admit the importance of the cooperation in the region. The digital and e-commerce initiatives conducted by the two countries are admitted to increasing cooperation in the sector, and in the context, it admits the contribution of India's IT Company particularly located in Cyberjaya. Malaysia will build the first Digital Trade Zone in the world. It will give potential profit for businessmen by offering a conducive environment for digital companies to carry out the exciting internet-based innovation. Therefore, it catalyzes Malaysia's economy. The initiative is part of the National E-Commerce Strategic Roadmap recently launched with the purpose of doubling the e-commerce growth in the country from 10.8% to 20.8% in 2020.

Moreover, India is Singapore's natural business partner. The country undergoes urbanization quickly, and it has stipulated to build 100 smart cities. Singapore, the urban city country, is ready to be India's partner in this

journey and it helps to develop the urban solution on the basis of their own experiences. New capital city of Amaravati in Andhra Pradesh and it is an example. As the chairman of ASEAN countries, Singapore has the commitment to increase the ASEAN-Indian relationship. If the two parties use the cultural and historical relationship, it will overcome the current obstacles, and it builds bridges for the future, new generation and our successor generation to get the best things. The financial industry in Singapore absolutely should be supported with good technology capacity. For this matter, cooperation between India and Singapore in the financial technology sector is a must (PTI 2018).

3.4 Adaptive Efforts and Indonesia's Anticipation

Indonesia is the biggest archipelago country in the world with a great population. The condition looks like India. We make cooperation, and it starts with the initiative of digital connectivity in the region. We can fulfill telecommunication demand in ASEAN. Indonesia will become potential and strategic market for India. The demand for Indonesia's telecommunication project is very high for the development of internet basis, the aggressive e-government project, broadband, and others. Therefore, India's government seriously proves the ability of IT and telecommunication sector by creating innovation and research and development center for various global class apparatuses. The cooperation basis in the digital sector between India and ASEAN is extensive experience and power that we have with ASEAN countries. India's power in the sector of ICT, finance and the government's support in the infrastructure development in India is seen with the government's commitment to developing a fiber-optic broadband network with a total range of 250,000 kilometers connecting all villages in Indonesia has made it optimistic to do the digital business expansion to Indonesia.

As it was known in the 13th ASEAN-India Summit Meeting in November 2015, India's Prime Minister Narendra Modi has carried out the Line of Credit with a total value of US\$1 billion. It will promote the projects supporting physical and digital connectivity between India and ASEAN. India has proved its ability in the sector of Information and Communication Technology. The country is admitted as the chosen destination for telecommunication products and services with telecommunication product technology transfer designed through the research and development for the demands of developing countries.

Head of Capital Investment Coordinating Agency (BKPM) Thomas Lembong states that for Indonesia it is great big to making cooperation with India in this matter. Either India or Indonesia is under "boom" period of the digital economy. However, Indonesia's electronic traders mostly use programmers and coding services from India. Many e-commerce in Indonesia utilizes India's programmers and coding services. Indonesia is in the booming of the digital economy, but it is lack of programmers (bkpm 2018).

In fact, Indonesia should carry out substantive and real efforts so that they can increase capacity in the programmer sector. It is very important because information technology is a vulnerable and expensive business sector if it is not totally under the control of the state, it will be difficult for Indonesia to hunt the lag. The compensation politics is required in this matter. Indonesia's society will not only be advantaged with the business expansion, but it will be disadvantaged for the expansion that does not have a clear agreement in relation to technology transfer to Indonesia's human resources.

Compensation politics should be carried out because not all people have access to capital and capacity of competition with other countries. It is usually carried out for poor people because they undergo difficulty in encountering life in a country with the liberal system. It is an idea to give compensation to Indonesia's businessmen, who are a disadvantaged condition, then it is not outside product, but there is unbalance technology transfer. Indonesia's businessmen and human resources should get compensation because at least they are part of Indonesia and finally they will only serve for Indonesia in the future.

4. Conclusion

Firstly, Indonesia should allocate greater fund for the collaboration with information technology businessmen and startup so that the country should at least have a legal and personal approach to Indonesia's IT business owners. If human resources from India develop IT business here, Indonesian society will only become viewers. In fact, high-technology business potentially can create significant dependency in the inter-country business and economic relationship.

Secondly, compensation politics is basically the state's effort to give the disadvantaged parties compensation from the existing system and economic-political structure. The compensation can be carried out in any kind that the society can accept. For the purpose, building the capacity in a kind of developing human resources, such as

the building of coworking house and the IT laboratory for anyone who wants to study it deeply is the government's efforts that have to be done. At least public feels they get facilities from the state for their interest development and in one time, it will be useful for the state.

Thirdly, regulations on workers' composition in each business agreement with other countries or companies of other countries are an effort that should be carried out. Indeed the government occasionally wants to execute the approved projects, but it is wise if the renegotiation will be carried out so that Indonesia's society will be trained and involved in various IT prospective businesses.

In fact, the efforts have been carried out to bridge Indonesia's unreadiness against definitely hard competition in the economic and business sector. Appropriate to the constitution, a state has to protect its citizens and the disqualified parties in a kind of cooperation policy with other countries. Don't make Indonesian people lost for the cooperation. In fact, the cooperation is intended to build the nation. Or if it makes lost, the government should carry out the qualified compensation politics. Therefore, the disadvantaged parties can receive it.

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